

IMPACT OF SWAT CONFLICT ON LIVESTOCK SECTOR

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Abstract: *Conflict has been a common feature throughout the world in its long history. Pakistan is no exception to such undesirable incidences. In 2009 Pakistan Army launched an operation against the rebellions in Swat and about 2.5 million of people became refugees and migrated to the neighboring safe places. The study was undertaken with the objective to analyze the impact of the conflict on livestock sector in Swat area. Stratified random sampling was used to ascertain a sample of 100 respondents. Data was collected through structured questionnaire and analyzed by using STATA and SPSS. The study revealed that conflict reduced the average number of livestock by 26 percent in the fully affected sample areas and 19 percent in the partially affected sample areas. Monthly income from the sale of livestock products decreased by 54% in the fully affected sample areas and 16.5% in the partially affected areas whereas the average annual income from the sale of live animals decreased by 62% in the fully affected and 5.5% in the partially affected tehsils. There was a significant difference in livestock losses during conflict subject to education level, farming experience and number of adult male family members. The conflict changed the employment composition of the households with a decline of 6.45 percent on the farm employment whereas the male migration was adopted as strategy to work abroad which increased by 50 and 100 percent in the fully and partially affected tehsils respectively to augment their families income and cope with the shocks of the conflict.*

Keywords: Conflict, Swat, household assets, livestock losses, trees losses.

Introduction

During armed conflict civilian population faces large assets losses. The civilians are targeted by the armed groups to seize their valuable assets and expand territory control (Azam and Hoefler, 2002). Assets play a significant role in the household wellbeing as these provide

income and protection against the risks in future contingencies. Land, livestock and other assets are used to cope with any unwanted situation (Little et al, 2006; Helme and Shepherd, 2003). Livestock is considered as capital asset, and has key role in reducing poverty (Uptin, 2004). It helps to increase agricultural income (Bruck, 2004). Armed conflict could have a dramatic impact on livestock number. Animals could be killed, stolen or succumb to disease due to the collapse of the veterinary services and cattle herding becomes unfeasible in the conflict areas (WFP-Somalia, 1995; Bruck, 2004). During the ten years armed conflict from 1982 to 1992 in Mozambique, the number of livestock was decreased from 1.3 million to 0.25 (Bruck, 2004). The armed conflict of Ghana destroyed the livestock industry which was the source of livelihood of millions of households in the region. Most of the livestock farmers in the conflict zone have not fully recovered from losses even after a decade (Addah and Zezebi, 2008). Pakistan has no exception to undesirable incidences and has faced conflicts in one form or the other since its independence. Pakistan faced the worst conflict of its history when foreign elements with local supporters hijacked the valley of Swat and armed clashes broke out in the area in 2006. In conflict scenario, aggression by armed groups against the rural population deteriorates agricultural income through the seizure of land, the stealing of livestock and or the destruction of productive assets. The households are forced to rely on non-agriculture activities to compensate for drops in agricultural income. Their wellbeing is highly compromised. They are forced to sell their productive assets and to reduce expenditures on food, health and education. The same was true in Swat conflict. Despite its scenic value and tourism Swat valley has significant importance for its contribution to agricultural production (Ali, 2010). The total effect during 17 months of war from crop production alone was Rs. 7914 million (Zahid, 2009). Swat conflict badly affected the local agricultural economy and livelihood of the people. In the history of world first time around three millions of people displaced from their homes and became “Internally Displaced People (IDPs)” who left their crops, livestock and other property behind for safety of their lives (Khan, 2007). Previous studies have reported the adverse impact of the conflict on agricultural productivity and livestock strength. The role of certain assets with limited context has also been studied. However, a detailed study with reference to the impact of Swat conflict on livestock and subsequent impact on household wellbeing has not yet been carried out. It is assumed that livestock losses may comprise the future welfare of household, thus leaving a legacy of structural poverty that is difficult to overcome. The focus of this research is to examine whether and how conflict damages the livestock of the households and ultimately influences the wellbeing of the household. The specific objectives are as under

1. To measure the impact of armed conflict on livestock strength.
2. To assess determinant of livestock income

METHODOLOGY:

Data Collection

In this study two different situations are estimated to see the impact of pre and post conflict state of affairs in terms of social and financial alterations. For this purpose primary data was collected through field survey of Swat district by using a well-structured

questionnaire. The tools used for data collection were household interviews, key informants interviews, focus group discussions and participant observations. For the tabulation and analysis of data Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSS), Excel and Stata were used. The period selected for the study was two years. One year before the conflict (2008) and one year after the conflict (2010), main focus was given to the time before displacement and to the time when Internally Displaced People (IDPs) returned. The universe of the study was Swat district of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province of Pakistan and in order to collect the requisite information, single stage stratified random sampling technique was used. For detailed study two conflict affected *tehsils* (where all the villages were affected) Charbagh and Matta and two partially effected *tehsils* (where some villages were affected and the others were not) Khwazakhela and Babozi were selected to compare the impact of armed conflict on fully affected and partially affected *tehsils*.

A sample of 100 households was drawn randomly from the selected four *tehsils* for detailed enumeration and data collection purposes by using well-structured questionnaire.

Paired t-test

For the analysis of pre-conflict and post-conflict data paired t-test was employed.

$$T = \frac{\bar{d}}{SE(\bar{d})} \quad \text{(With n-1 d.f)}$$

Where

$$\bar{d} = \frac{\sum d_i}{n}$$

$$SE(\bar{d}) = \frac{sd}{\sqrt{n}} \quad \text{Where}$$

d_i = pre conflict assets – post conflict assets of the household.

sd = standard deviation of d_i values.

\bar{d} = mean value of the differences between pre-conflict and post-conflict assets.

A confidence interval for the mean difference was calculated to know within what limits the true difference is likely to lie. The confidence interval for the true mean difference is given as.

OLS technique

To identify the role of different determinants in households’ livestock income OLS technique was employed. Similar techniques were used by Kondylis (2007) and Suzuki (2007) to identify factors which significantly affect the households’ incomes.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Income}(Y) = & \beta_1 + \beta_2 M_{\text{buff}} + \beta_3 D_{\text{buff}} + \beta_4 \text{buffYS} + \beta_5 M_{\text{cow}} + \beta_6 D_{\text{cow}} \\
 & + \beta_7 \text{cowYS} + \beta_8 \text{Goat} + \beta_9 \text{Oprholding} + \beta_{10} \text{Edu} + \beta_{11} \text{Exp} + \beta_{12} \text{famsys} \\
 & + \beta_{13} \text{AdultM} + e
 \end{aligned}$$

Where

Y	=	Households livestock income
M _{buff}	=	Number of milking buffalos
D _{buff}	=	Number of Dry buffalos
buffYS	=	Number Buffalo young stock
M _{cow}	=	Number of milking Cows
D _{cow}	=	Number of dry cows
cowYS	=	Number of cow young stock
Goat	=	Number of goats
Oprholding	=	Operational holding
Edu	=	Education level
Exp	=	Experience level
Famsys	=	Family system
AdultM	=	Adult Male members

RESULTS

Socioeconomic Profile of the Sample Farmers

The information about the socioeconomic characteristics of the farmers and their farms are important for decision making. During the survey, it was found worthwhile to choose the older respondents to gather maximum desired information. The average age of the sample respondents was more than 43 years with a mean farming experience as 24.3 years. The average family size was estimated of 12 members and all the sample farmers were educated with an average 6.1 years of schooling (Table 1).

Most of the people of the sample area live in joint family system as revealed in the survey that 58 percent of the farmers belonged to the joint family system (Table 4.1). On the average before the armed conflict 2.17 persons of the family were working full time on their farms which was reduced to 2.03 persons because of the conflict. The main reason of the decline in the average number of on farm was the migration of the people abroad. Therefore, the number of male working abroad the country was increased to 0.44 as it was 0.19 before the armed conflict.

Table 1 Socioeconomic Characteristics of the Sample Farmers

Characteristic	Mean Value	St. Deviation
Age of Respondent (Years)	43.70	14.70
Farming Experience (Years)	24.30	12.90
Households Family Size	12.00	7.40
Education (Years)	6.10	5.50
Joint Family system (%)	58.00	-
Male working full time on farm BC*	2.17	1.52
Male working full time on farm AC*	2.03	1.32
No. of male working abroad BC	0.19	0.44
No. of male working abroad AC	0.31	0.65
BC* = Before Conflict AC* = After Conflict		

Source: Field Survey

Livestock Strength Before and After Conflict (Number of Animals)

Livestock is known an integral part of all types of farming systems and it contributes a lot both for income and consumption (e.g. through the sale of milk) as well as physical asset and symbol of social status in rural societies (Akmal *et al.*, 2004).

The data in table 2 shows the average number of livestock before and after the conflict. A decrease in the number of animals was observed for overall livestock on average, except for the goats in both fully affected and partially effected *tehsils*. In fully affected *tehsils*, statistically significant difference before and after the conflict can be observed in case of livestock average number except buffalo young stock. The average number of buffalo young stock had t-value more than 2.4. Partially effected *tehsils* show a decrease in livestock but it is not statistically significant except dry buffalo as it has t-value of 3. The number of goats was increased in both fully effected and partially effected *tehsils* as goats were donated by an international non-governmental organization (Oxfam) to the rural conflict affected households (Table 2).

During the armed conflict, 78% of the households sold their animals at less than half of the market price to finance their daily consumption needs. The second reason of decrease in number of livestock was that it was difficult to shift their livestock with them during displacement. Out of total sample farmers,12% reported that they had lost their livestock in heavy bombardment or burning down their houses by the security forces especially in fully affected *tehsils* and due to the collapse of the veterinary and extension services in the area.

Table 2 Livestock strength before and after conflict (Average number of animals)

Fully affected tehsils	Partially affected tehsils
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Cattle Name	Average No. of Animal		Mean Difference	t-value	Avg. No. of Animal		Mean Difference	t-value
	BC	AC			BC	AC		
Milking Buffalo	1.94	1.18	0.76*	4.19	1.96	1.50	0.47**	2.04
Dry Buffalo	2.0	1.60	0.40*	2.71	1.75	1.00	0.75*	3.00
Buffalo (Young Stock)	1.75	1.50	0.25	1.0	1.80	1.40	0.40	1.00
Milking Cow	1.90	1.18	0.73*	3.10	1.42	1.07	0.36	2.10
Dry Cow	1.80	1.20	0.60*	2.45	1.67	1.33	0.33	1.00
Cow (Young Stock)	2.14	1.14	1.0*	2.65	2.14	1.86	0.29	1.00
Goat	1.14	2.0	-0.5	-1.0	1.69	1.84	-0.15	-0.25
Total	12.67	9.8	3.24		12.43	10	2.45	

*Highly significant
 **Significant at 5%

Source: Field Survey

Determinants of income from livestock

The income from livestock depends on various factors where the role of number of milking buffalos is dominant. Increase in the average number of milking buffalo by one percent resulted significant increase of 0.92 percent in the income from livestock products whereas the dry buffalo and young stock of buffalo decreased the income from livestock products by 0.11 and 0.02 percent respectively. Milking and dry cow also increased the income from livestock products by 0.22 and 0.07 percent at 1 and 10 percent significance levels respectively. Increase in the average number of young stock of cows cause a decrease in the mean income by 0.09 percent at 5 percent level of significance whereas increase in the number of goats has a negative effect of 0.0029 percent. Livestock strength, operational holding, farming experience, joint family system and adult male has a positive but insignificant effect on the mean income by 0.018, 0.010, 0.032, 0.056 and 0.02 percent respectively. Charbagh (Dummy), Matta (Dummy) and Khwazakhela (Dummy) has a positive effect of 0.082, 0.022 and 0.041 percent respectively with a 10% significance level for Charbagh and insignificant for other two (Matta and Khwazakhela). Education has also negative coefficient indicating that increase in the mean level of education cause a decrease in the income from livestock products by 0.004 percent.

Table 3 Determinants of Income from Livestock

Determinants	Coefficients	t-value
Income from Livestock Products		
(Constant)	5706.05	1.66
Milking Buffalo	0.928*	23.71
Dry Buffalo	-0.117*	-3.0
Buffalo (Young stock)	-0.029	-0.78
Milking Cow	0.229*	5.64
Dry Cow	0.073***	1.83
Cow (Young stock)	-0.093**	-2.22
Goat	-0.003	-0.08
Charbagh	0.083***	1.67
Matta	0.022	0.46
Khwazakhela	0.041	0.86
Livestock number	0.019	0.46
Operational land holding	0.011	0.28
Education level (Years)	-0.005	-0.12
Farming Experience (Years)	0.032	0.76
Familysystem; 1=joint, 2=nuclear	0.057	1.42
Number of adult males	0.020	0.43
*Highly significant **significant at 5%, ***weakly significant $R^2 = 0.90$ Adj $R^2 = 0.88$		

Source: Field Survey

Changes in Households Income and Milk Production

The armed conflict had a devastating impact on livestock numbers and hence milk production. Conflict considerably reduced milk production and declined a household's ability to secure food. The fully affected *tehsils* show highly significant decrease in milk production. Before the conflict average milk production was estimated to be 23.1 liters/day which reduced to 10.4 liters/day after the conflict whereas in the partially affected *tehsils* it significantly decreased from 24 to 18 liters/day. Significant decrease in milk production had also reduced the average selling of milk from the pre-conflict scenario. The average selling of the milk in the fully affected *tehsils* reduced from 13.9 to 5.0 liters/day which is statistically significant difference and the partially affected *tehsils* have also a decrease in milk selling from 15.1 to 12 liters/day but that remains statistically insignificant (Table 4).

Statistically significant decrease has been found in net income earned from the sale of livestock products in the fully affected *tehsils*, the average monthly income after the conflict decreased from Rs. 14178.5 to Rs. 6565.3 whereas in the partially affected *tehsils* the average monthly income was recorded Rs. 13600.4 before the conflict which was decreased to Rs. 11359.6 after the conflict.

Households’ annual income earned from the sale of live animals was also badly affected in the area but statistically significant decrease was observed only in the fully affected *tehsils* as average annual income of the households decreased from 26054 to 9837 rupees whereas statistically insignificant decrease from Rs. 29096 to Rs. 27586 was observed in partially affected *tehsils* (Table 4).

Table 4 Changes in Households Annual Income and Milk Production

Fully affected tehsils					Partially affected tehsils			
	BC	AC	Difference	t-value	BC	AC	Difference	t-value
Average daily Milk Production/	23.1	10.4	12.7*	3.40	24.5	18.0	6.5*	2.48
Milk Sold (Liters) daily	13.9	5.0	8.9*	3.24	15.1	12.0	3.1***	1.78
Average Monthly income from sale of livestock products	14178.5	6565.3	7613.2*	2.49	13600.4	11359.6	2240.8	1.00
Average Annual Income from Sale live Animal	26054	9837	16217*	4.50	29096	27586	1510	1.43
*Highly significant **significant at 5% ***weakly significant								

Source: Field Survey

DISCUSSION

Changes in livestock strength

The number of livestock was decreased by 26 percent and by 19 percent in the fully affected and partially affected *tehsils*, respectively. Forced displacement was the main reason as almost the whole population migrated to different regions of the country during conflict. Households sold their livestock at less than half of the market price to finance their daily expenditures. The death of the animals due to the collapse of veterinary services and the unavailability of fodder during conflict were the other reasons of decrease in the livestock strength. Some other studies found a decrease in the strength of livestock from 50-56 percent during the armed conflicts (Justino, 2011; World Bank, 2011). The reason of the difference

between the level of damage registered in previous studies and this particular study seems to be due to the duration of the armed conflict.

Determinants of income from livestock

In 3 *tehsils* of the study areas; Charbagh, Matta and Khwazakhela, most of the people depend on incomes from their livestock. Milking animals play an important role in rural incomes. The positive coefficient of milking animals, especially milking buffalo, showed that with the increase in the number of milking buffalos the income increased. Regression analysis showed that increase in the number of milking buffalo significantly increased income from sale the of livestock products especially from increased milk production. Dry animals and young stocks decrease the income from the sale of livestock products because they share the fodder which already in short supply and thus affect the production of milk from milking animals whereas they contribute nothing to the current income from livestock products. Despite the negative effect on the income from livestock products people keep them because their value increases with passage of time which contributes to the future income of the farmers. The positive effect of operational holding is due to the fact that farmers retain as many animals as they can because they face no problem regarding fodder and grazing. Farming experience and the joint family system also enhances the income from livestock. Farming experience played a key role in farming income as the level of experience increased they became more aware of the importance of livestock in income generation on the one hand and its beneficial effects on the crops on the other. Experience also enhances management skills and enables the farmer to manage large number of livestock. Similar studies also found that land holding, livestock and rich farming experience are positively related with livestock income (Akram *et al.*, 2011). Joint family system ensures the economic use of the milk for domestic consumption which enables the farmers to sell more milk and other dairy products and enhance their income from the sale of livestock products. It is astonishing to reveal that the level of education has negative effect on livestock income as with the increase in the level of education income from livestock decreases. However, income from other sources increased with increase in education level. A relevant study conducted in China showed that education did not influence farm incomes whereas non-farm earnings primarily depended on education level (de Janvry *et al.*, 2005).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conflict affected every sphere of the life which changed the strategies for the future life. Finding of the study revealed that conflict reduced the average number of livestock by 26 percent in the fully affected *tehsils* and 19 percent in the partially affected *tehsils* due to sale of animals during displacement, unavailability of feed, difficulties in open grazing, collapse of veterinary services and death of animals during conflict. Monthly income from the sale of livestock products decreased significantly by 54 percent in the fully affected *tehsils* and 16.5 percent in the partially affected *tehsils* because the number of milking animals decreased whereas the decline in the average annual income from the sale of live animals was 62 and 5.2 percent respectively for the above mentioned *tehsils*.

In order to strengthen the livestock sector in the conflict affected Swat productive and healthy species of livestock to be provided to the farmers, veterinary services should be ensured taking care of existing livestock. Local buffalos (Achai) should be conserved. Measures should be taken to increase milk productivity of the animals.

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